

METAPHORS IN BUSINESS DISCOURSE

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Figurative language has always been used in business communication, with metaphoric expressions being its most representative and frequent elements. A metaphor is defined as a transference of literary meaning of a word into another context, which means that one thing is described in terms of some other thing, e. g. time is money, cash cow, sleeping beauty. It is the notion of either comparison or resemblance that creates the basis for the metaphor – instead of the literal meaning of a word or expression native language users can easily produce a metaphoric expression and understand its figurative meaning. Metaphors are culture-specific and they reveal patterns of thought that are characteristic of individuals and of groups. Business English metaphors can, and indeed do, reflect the values, beliefs and norms that prevail in the language of business communication in English-speaking countries and in many global companies. Figurative expressions are frequently found to be the preferred way of conveying meaning in the language of business and business communicators tend to use metaphoric expressions both in written and spoken discourse. Therefore, the role of high-frequency metaphoric expressions in the language of business communication needs to be explored in greater detail. Analysis of these metaphoric expressions from the point of view of applied linguistics can shed some more light on the nature of business communication. The aim of the paper is to present the most popular business metaphors, suggest a classification of these expressions, to analyze their most common classes and to identify their role in today's business communication.

Today metaphors are generally accepted in the language of business communication and they are widely used in business discourse. Metaphor means transference of a word from one context into another; metaphor is described as «a means by which one thing is described in terms of something else» [7, p. X]. It is the notion of either comparison or resemblance that creates the basis for the metaphor – instead of the literal meaning of a word or expression native language users can easily produce a metaphor and understand its figurative meaning. Metaphors add variety, imagery, spice and colour to the language. Thanks to metaphors business English users can express their views, feelings and opinions in a stronger, and sometimes more emotional way. Lakoff and Johnson [4] are of the opinion that metaphoric expressions reflect the metaphorical nature of the concepts that structure our everyday activities. They claim that most of the ordinary conceptual system people create is metaphorical in nature and that our cognition is metaphorical. Thus the conceptual system used in thinking is reflected in the conceptual system on which communication is based. Metaphor reveals patterns of thought that are characteristic of individuals and of groups. Some popular business metaphors, e. g. advertising campaign are used in many European languages. Thornbury says that people «resort to and depend on the use of metaphor when it comes to verbalizing their experience: metaphors help them to see what is invisible, to describe what otherwise would be indescribable» [9, p. 193]. Metaphoric expressions have been extensively studied by psychologists, cognitive linguists, sociologists and philosophers but not by applied linguists. «While the role of metaphor in language has been a focus of

considerable interest in linguistics and other fields since the pioneering work of Lakoff and Johnson and has been the focus of several thousand journal articles, it has received much less attention within applied linguistics» [7, p.X]. The role of high-frequency metaphoric expressions in the language of business communication needs to be explored in greater detail. Analysis of these metaphoric expressions from the point of view of applied linguistics can shed some more light on the nature of business communication. The aim of the paper is to present the most popular business metaphors, suggest a classification of these expressions, to analyze their most common classes and to identify their role in today's business communication. First the paper presents a list of selected high-frequency metaphors used in the language of business communication. The list is organized in two ways: (1) formally – according to the structure of the metaphor, and (2) semantically – according to the concept underlying a given metaphor. These two categorizations will be followed by examples of 'novel' business metaphors excerpted from a corpus of articles published in the Wall Street Journal.

2. Examples of metaphors used in business communication

In the language of business communication metaphors reflect the way of thinking. Cameron and Low in their book *Researching and Applying Metaphor* [2] say that metaphor is fundamental to the way language systems develop over time and to the way human beings consolidate and extend their ideas about themselves, their relationships and their knowledge of the world. A classical Arabic saying that a metaphor is the bridge to reality seems to be true as metaphor «links and comprises the known and the unknown, the tangible and the less tangible, the familiar and the new» [1, p. 149]. Longman Dictionary of Language Teaching and Applied Linguistics says that «metaphors are important means by which words carry both cultural and semantic meanings, and each language has its own metaphors that have been accumulated over time» [8, c. 201]. This statement helps to explain why metaphoric expressions are widely used in business communication practice. Nowadays, people often perceive doing business as a fight in which only the strongest and the fittest can survive. In a fiercely competitive world of business companies have to fight to be better than their rivals. They have to develop marketing strategies and advertising campaigns in order to trigger sales. They need a good leader; usually it is the Chief Executive Officer, often supported by the Chief Financial Officer. A successful businessman is like a hunter, a shark or a predator that has a competitive advantage over his rivals and is able to win more orders and enter new markets. As a result of such an attitude to business dealings, the language of business communication is rich in metaphors of fight and war.

Business also means risk and profit. In business the name of the game is profit and profit is always accompanied by a certain degree of risk. In high-risk ventures one faces huge risk but hopefully can expect windfall profits. Handsome profits are likely to attract many potential investors. However, if you fail to assess risk properly, you are likely to suffer heavy losses and you may even find it impossible to recover from crisis. Even if you use creative accounting and try to cook the books, it may not help and in the worst case scenario you may even find that your company is at the edge of bankruptcy. Sometimes a business organization is perceived as a big family in which we may have paternalistic leadership, junior and senior managers, junior and senior positions, a parent company, a mother company or a sister company. Many people think that an organization is like a living organism (head of department, new blood, fresh blood); sometimes they also attribute personality traits to a business organization (a company

is open, responsible, friendly, and innovative). Human resources are considered to be an important constituent in a successful business organization. Good employees are a valuable asset; they deserve an evergreen contract accompanied by a good pay package including many fringe benefits, and preferably a cafeteria plan. If they are high flyers they have a chance to go up the career ladder. If they are success-driven high performers they are likely to be promoted to higher positions and receive golden handcuffs. When they retire, they may receive a golden handshake. The above examples of metaphors frequently used in the language of business show the significance of figurative expressions in real-life communication. They also demonstrate why figurative language cannot be ignored in ESP research. If we understand the role of metaphoric expressions in business communication, we can use them more skillfully in order to improve the effectiveness of communication. Business dealings can be easier if partners understand each other well.

Using metaphors adds authenticity to the language of business communication and enriches it. One fundamental question, however, that non-native speakers of English need to ask is what kinds of metaphors and which metaphors to use. It seems justified that only the metaphors that are well-established in the language of business communication should be used. Such well-established metaphors, which are no longer perceived as metaphors (e. g. we are open to suggestions, face a challenge, head office, make an offer, lower the price), deserve incorporation into the language of business communication. Non-native speakers are exposed to a variety of metaphoric expressions in authentic business texts. However, it seems reasonable that they should use the most popular, so called 'dead' metaphors only and try not to experiment with 'living' metaphors.

Metaphor is often treated as a peripheral rather than central part of language description. Metaphor is, however, a natural and frequent component of business communication and it deserves attention [3, 5, 6]. The paper presents over 500 most popular 'dead' business metaphors and classifies them according to (1) their formal structure and (2) the concept underlying a given metaphor. It is hoped that the presented categorization of popular metaphors may be helpful in a better description of business English. It is also hoped that the paper may contribute to increased awareness of the importance of figurative language in business communication.

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